

LiveSeeding Project website and social media

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LiveSeeding - Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe is a 4-year Innovation Action funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project started in October 2022 and brings together 37 organisations operating in 15 European countries. LiveSeeding provides science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help achieve 100 % organic seed.

LiveSeeding contributes to the transition towards environmentally-friendly, climate-neutral, healthy and fair food systems through a **PUSH-PULL-ENABLE** strategy to

- enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PUSH),
- increase and stabilise the market demand for organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PULL),
- foster an enabling policy and regulatory environment where both demand and supply can harmoniously and productively negotiate without irrelevant constraints due to legal restrictions and/or regulatory fragmentation (ENABLE).

LiveSeeding addresses the topics in a **holistic multi-actor, multi-stakeholder, participatory approach** involving stakeholders along the value chain in 17 local **Living Labs (LLs)** and 3 established networks of organic breeders (**ECO-PB**), seed savers (**ECLLD**) and Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (**MUFPP**). 15 European countries cover the different pedoclimatic zones and socio-economic contexts, including countries with a low level of development in organic seed and breeding in East and South Europe.

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List of abbreviations

ECLLD	European Coordination Let's Liberate Diversity
ECO-PB	The European Consortium for Organic plant breeding
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability
IPC	Instituto Politecnico de Coimbra
LL	Living Lab
MUFPP	Milan Urban Food Policy Pact
OA	Open Access
SERI	Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
WP	Work package

Summary

This deliverable presents the LiveSeeding project website, its structure, and the description of each section. LiveSeeding's website is designed in a simple and user-friendly way, and it will function as a depository of all project results that are under Open Access (OA). The content of the project website will be regularly updated by WP7 leaders (IPS Konzalting) based on content provided by the partners.

The project website is designed to promote the project and disseminate the project outputs to the wider public (stakeholders, policy makers, scientists outside the project, citizens and public).

Some pages of the website are more descriptive and static, such as pages

- Project overview, governance and structure
- The LiveSeeding project "roots" (LIVESEED project)
- Section on contact persons

Other are more dynamic and interactive, and provide functionalities to:

- Access the LiveSeeding SharePoint (via login and password) for project partners
- Register to the project newsletter and stakeholder database
- Access/make use of resources, participate in trainings and events, engage on Living Labs
- Search the website content via 2 criteria "I am" and "I am interested in" and several categories within it
- Categorize materials, news and information uploaded on the website pages, making use of "tags" or "key words"

The language used for the website structure and sections is English, but it will be possible to upload documents and materials in several languages.

1. Homepage

The homepage header contains the project Logo and a horizontal bar with the 7 menu items:

- **LIVESEEDING**
- **Project activities**
- **News & Media**
- **Resources**
- **Events & Trainings**
- **Living Labs**
- **Seed policy**

On the homepage, website visitors can:

- Navigate the website through the menu in the header
- Sign up to the newsletter using a dedicated box
- Select under "I am" a category of stakeholder group they belong to (e.g., seed producer, policy maker, farmer, seed researcher, citizens or other) and/or under "I am interested in" which area they are interested in (e.g., policy work, events & trainings, knowledge transfer, scientific results, or market opportunities) to focus their navigation/search
- Access/be redirected to the LiveSeeding internal collaborative workspace (LiveSeeding SharePoint) with a login/password system (restricted to LiveSeeding project partners)

MENU						
LIVESEEDING	Project activities	News & Media	Resources	Events & trainings	Living Labs	Seed policy
Project objectives	Project structure	Latest news	Videos	Trainings & Summer School	About Living Labs	Policy briefs & recommendations
Project partners*	WP1	Media corner	Booklets & Practice abstracts	Conferences	Living Lab events	EU Organic Seed Database
Project governance	WP2	Newsletters	Deliverables & Publications	Field demo days		Local food policies
Collaboration network	WP3					
Funding source	WP4					
	WP5					
Our roots LIVESEED project	WP6					
About the project						
LIVESEED resources						
Contact & disclaimer						

Figure 1: Front page of the LiveSeeding website and LiveSeeding web structure

2. Website Menu “LIVESEEDING”

The LIVESEEDING Menu includes five submenus about the LIVESEEDING project and one about LIVESEED project (the previous EU funded project LiveSeeding is a continuation of and builds on), called “Our roots – LIVESEED project”. The submenus will be described below.

2.1. Project in a nutshell

Project in a nutshell presents main objective of the LIVESEEDING project, structure of LIVESEEDING Work Packages (WP) and main project ambitions.

LIVESEEDING Work Packages (WP)

Figure 2: Structure of LIVESEEDING Work Packages

In the part of project ambitions, the push-pull-enable strategy is clearly presented and described graphically.

Figure 3: Push-Pull-Enable strategy

2.2 Project partners

In this submenu, the entire project consortium of the LIVESEEDING project is presented, which includes 37 partners from 16 countries (14 EU plus Switzerland and the United Kingdom). Clicking on an individual partner will lead to their website.

Figure 4: View of “Project partners” section

2.3 Project governance

This submenu provides information (the contact details such as address, website, contact person) about 3 main project governance and management bodies:

- Executive Committee (ExCom) – composed of WP leaders and coleaders
- Project Coordinator, Scientific Coordinators (Innovation Management - IM) and Communication Coordinator
- IPR board and Stakeholder Group.

2.4 Collaboration network

In this” submenu, visitors can find information about:

- IAB – International Advisory Board made of external persons not directly involved in the project, providing strategic advice to the project on the basis of their expertise
- A list of related “sister” projects and their brief description (such as BRESOV, DIVERSIFOOD, ECOBREED, InnOBreed...). These projects have similar topics as LiveSeeding and contribute to the aim to bring the achievements of the latest projects on organic plant breeding to practice and to address the research gaps not explored or newly highlighted in these initiatives
- An overview of European networks in which the LiveSeeding project will be active

Figure 5: View of “Collaboration network” section

2.5 Funding source

This submenu provides information about project donors and their emblems for acknowledgement and visibility purposes.

Figure 6: LIVESEEDING donors acknowledgement and emblems

2.6 Our roots – LIVESEED project

LiveSeeding project builds on the experience and results of the LIVESEED project, funded by the EU under the Horizon 2020 programme and concluded in 2021.

This section presents the main objectives, scope and structure (Work Packages and Tasks) of LIVESEED and key resources, such as Deliverables, are made available for long term curation and dissemination purposes. Project highlights and key results are also listed and complements with graphs.

3. Website Menu “Project Activities”

This menu provides insight into the project structure, a brief description of work packages, as well as their main objectives. Each part is clearly described and adapted to the specific website visitors/targets of the sections and accompanied by graphs elements for better visibility.

3.1 Project structure

In “Project structure” sub-menu the main objectives of the LiveSeeding project are presented under different WPs. Figure 4 shows the description and main objectives of the Work Package 1 and the list of tasks contained within WP1, as an example for all sections. Other work packages are presented in the same way as WP1.

The image is a screenshot of a website menu for Work Package 1. At the top, there is a green banner with the text "WP1 - Increase and manage crop diversity (pre-breeding & breeding)". Below the banner, there are two columns of text. The left column describes the goal of enhancing crop performance through crop diversity. The right column discusses breeding for organic systems and lists three levels of diversity: between cultivars, within-cultivar, and species diversity. At the bottom, a dark teal box contains a summary statement about pushing adoption of diverse cultivars on the market.

WP1 - Increase and manage crop diversity (pre-breeding & breeding)

To enhance and stabilise crop performance, organic farmers need a plurality of crops and cultivars adapted to a wide range of environments and organic farming systems, with high adaption potential and stress tolerance to tackle climate change.

Breeding for organic requires adopting a systems approach for which diversity is key. This is necessary on at least three levels:

- diversity between available cultivars to harness genotype by environment by management interactions and target local adaptation
- increasing within-cultivar diversity to enable resilience and evolutionary breeding
- increasing species diversity through more species, longer rotations and crop mixtures (intercropping, agroforestry) supported by appropriate cultivars

WP1 will push adoption of cultivars with a higher genetic variability and broader biodiversity potential on the market by accelerating use of genetic resources on farm, developing breeding strategies and innovative tools to target relevant traits for organic crop production and delivering candidates for OHM notification and OV registration.

LIVESEEDING project strengthens the interplay between ex situ conservation, on-farm dynamic management, pre-breeding and breeding through a more integrative and transdisciplinary approach involving genetics and breeding methods, scientific knowledge in functional ecology and agronomy as well as practical knowledge based on farmers and practitioners' experiences. Breeding of both OV and OHM will be addressed with emphasis on the level of intra-varietal/intra-population diversity that is desirable in different farming systems. Different breeding strategies and breeding tools will be applied, while addressing a wide range of crop species based expertise of partners and related LLs to foster broad innovation uptake.

Main objective of WP1 is to increase and optimize the available crop diversity to be used in organic farming systems.

Figure 7: Example of a work package view/description: WP 1

4. Website Menu “News & Media”

This menu contains 3 submenus: “Latest news”, “Media corner” and “Newsletters”.

Figure 8: View of the menu “News & Media”

4.1 Latest news

In “Latest news” section various project activities or events partners organise or participate in as well will be announced (e.g., conferences, workshops, Annual meeting, trials, etc).

4.2 Media corner

In submenu “Media corner” section will be posted news materials specifically targeting or dedicated to the media for further use (e.g. press releases). In this submenu, the media can find interesting information for them and contact project consortium.

4.3 Newsletters

LiveSeeding project will prepare biannual newsletters (every 6 months, in total 8 newsletters) and they will provide information such as:

- Updates on project implementation
- Project results
- Relevant news from the partners
- Information about project related conferences, workshops, trainings

Figure 9 View of the submenu “Newsletters”

5. Website Menu “Resources”

Within the “Resources” menu visitors will find various outputs and resources produced as part of the project, such as videos and booklets, practice abstracts & publications, as well as all other publicly available Deliverables.

Figure 10: View of the menu “Resources”

5.1 Videos

A short video on LiveSeeding project’s activities and expected impacts will be produced in English and subtitled in other languages and uploaded in this section. Also, videos of “success stories” will be produced in national languages and will be made available here.

5.2 Booklets & practice abstracts

Booklets and practice abstracts prepared during the project’s lifespan will be available in this section.

The innovative knowledge resulting from LiveSeeding will feed into the agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) website for broad dissemination to practitioners. End-user materials will be produced in the form of several summaries for practitioners in the EIP common format - "practice abstracts".

5.3 Deliverables & publications

In submenu “Deliverables & publications”, all project Deliverables and various project publications will be listed. Furthermore, all public Deliverables will be available for download in PDF version as they become available and approved by REA.

Figure 11: List of Deliverables (partial, example)

Various scientific publications, including open-access papers, book chapters, posters, etc., will be published during the project. The project publications and output materials will also be deposited in 3 main online repositories:

- Zenodo
- Organic Eprints
- Organic Farm Knowledge platform, section “Seed”

6. Website Menu “Events & trainings”

Within this menu there are 3 submenus: “Trainings & Summer School”, “Conferences” and “Field demo days”.

Figure 12: View of the menu “Events & trainings”

6.1 Trainings and Summer School

All training materials produced during the project lifespan will be made available in this section. Also, all information about the implementation of various trainings by the project partners will be available.

Broadly speaking this section will contain:

- Publicity about the training events to let potential targets people know about it and register
- Training materials
- Reports/photos, any follow up/outcomes of the trainings
- Training manuals

The summer school “Accelerating sustainable and diverse food systems through participatory organic plant breeding” based on project outcomes will be organised during the last year of the project, in cooperation with other EU and international projects on organic breeding and resilient seed systems. All important and relevant information about the Summer School as well as the different training modules will be made available here.

6.2 Conferences

LiveSeeding will organise one scientific conference (the target is the EUCARPIA Low input and Organic Agriculture section conference, which will take place in Portugal in 2025 with the main organiser IPC).

The final conference of the project will take place in Brussels in year 4 and will include a stakeholder section and a policy section.

Information about these conferences, information on registration and logistics, event agenda as well as other materials will be made available here.

6.3 Field demo days

On-field demonstration days are training events organised on organic farms, benefiting the Living Labs (LLs) participants, cross-WP study cases and other diverse food chain actors.

There will be more than 40 on-field demonstrations organised during the project's lifetime. Website visitors will be able to find information such as different farms involved, field trials, technical workshops, field visits, product tasting and workshops on dissemination and validation of the outcomes of the project. In this submenu, all important and relevant information for target audience will be available.

7. Website Menu “Living Labs”

7.1 Content of menu “Living Labs”

This menu provides information about the Living Labs and the Living Labs events.

Figure 13: View of the menu “Living Labs”

7.1.1 About Living Labs

“Living Labs” section provides important information about the 17 Living Labs described in the Grant Agreement. Website visitors will be able to find information such as:

- Living Lab name & stage
- Climatic area, EU zone
- Partners
- Value chain
- Seed companies/breeders
- Farmers & farmer associations

An interactive map of LiveSeeding Living Labs shows all the countries where Living Labs take place.

This section will allow visitors to get information either by:

- Crop: when putting the pointer (computer mouse) on a crop icons, a brief description of the LLs working on that particular crop will appear together with the following data: country, LL name & stage, value chain, seed company/breeders and farmers & farmer associations.
- Living Lab: Visual elements, pictures and a description of each Living Lab site visitors will be able to find.

In this submenu, all important and relevant information for target audience will be available.

Figure 14: View of “Living Labs” section

Figure 15: Map of LiveSeeding Living Labs

7.1.2 Living Lab events

Within the first 18 months of the project, each Living Lab will organise an opening event to plan in detail the activities to be conducted during the project. This submenu will include brief and user-friendly information about each of the opening events. Also, website visitors will be able to find information on how to participate and register for these events.

8. Website Menu “Seed policy”

8.1 Content of menu “Seed policy”

Menu “Seed policy” includes 3 submenus: “Policy briefs & recommendations”, “EU Organic Seed Database” and “Local food policies”.

Figure 16: View of the menu “Seed policy”

8.1.1 Policy briefs & recommendations

Submenu “Policy briefs” will provide document and materials to unlock the project outcomes for policymakers. The briefs will serve as the basis for knowledge dissemination to authorities on a national and European level.

8.1.2. EU Organic Seed Database

“European router database” enables plant reproductive material suppliers to manage their supply in all EU member states and Switzerland from one account.

Registered plant reproductive material suppliers can upload in the database information about their available organic plant reproductive material supply and indicate to which countries the individual offers can be delivered. This submenu will provide general information on the European Router Database and its main functions, and visitors will be able to access the Database via link that will also be presented in this submenu.

8.1.3 Local food policies

Recommendations and examples from other countries related to food and seed policy will be published and presented in this submenu.

9. “Contact and Disclaimer”

At the bottom of the website, visitors will find displayed contact information and a disclaimer.

Figure 17: View of the “Contact and Disclaimer” layout

10. Social media

Different social media channels, that are described below, will be useful to bring awareness about the project progress.

10.1 Twitter

Twitter, as one of the most popular social networking and microblogging service with the main characteristic that it allows short sentences, called tweets, will be used to publish short news, events, workshops, conferences, and progress of the LiveSeeding project to keep the stakeholders informed. LiveSeeding capitalised on the audience created under the LIVESEED project, so LIVESEED Twitter account was handed over to the LiveSeeding. All information on the home page is adapted to the LiveSeeding project (visual identity, logo, name, description of the project). IPS Konzalting is responsible for managing Twitter and preparing regular posts. At the time of writing, the LiveSeeding Twitter profile has 1796 followers.

@LIVESEEDING

<https://twitter.com/LIVESEEDING>

Figure 18: LiveSeeding LinkedIn page

10.2 Facebook

Facebook, as the most popular social media platform, with more than 2.9 billion users, will be used to raise awareness about the LiveSeeding project. IPS Konzalting is responsible for managing Facebook and updating on a regular basis as well. Same as for the Twitter, LiveSeeding capitalised on the Facebook audience created under the LIVESEED project and the LIVESEED Facebook page is adapted for the LiveSeeding. So far, the LiveSeeding Facebook profile has 1700 followers and 1400 likes.

@LIVESEEDING

<https://www.facebook.com/LIVESEEDING/>

Figure 19: LiveSeeding Facebook page

10.3 LinkedIn

A LinkedIn Profile has been created for LiveSeeding project that will provide partners a place to disseminate the project outputs and engage end users/stakeholder groups. So far, the LiveSeeding LinkedIn profile has 38 followers.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/liveseeding-project/>

Figure 20: LiveSeeding Twitter page

LiveSeeding

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